

UZBEKISTAN'S EXPERIENCE IN COMBATING TERRORISM AND EXTREMISM

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Abstract: The article considers a new approach to the socialization and rehabilitation of citizens who have fallen under the influence of destructive ideologies of state policy implemented in our country, based on the experience of the Republic of Uzbekistan in combating extremism and terrorism.

Keywords: Destructive ideas, propaganda and bitterness, socialization and rehabilitation, AVF, education and religious tolerance.

According to the International Institute of Economics and Peace, which conducts research on political, economic and social processes on a global scale, according to the global terrorism index, over the past ten years various terrorist acts have occurred in 164 countries of the world, the number of deaths as a result of them amounted to 182 thousand (in the previous decade, this figure was 72 thousand).

While Iraq, Nigeria, Syria, Somalia, Yemen, Pakistan, Afghanistan, India, Congo and the Philippines are among the top ten countries with the highest terrorism risk index, Uzbekistan ranks 134th out of 164 countries on this list. According to the High Terrorist Risk Index in 2020, the top ten high-risk countries included: Afghanistan, Iraq, Nigeria, Syria, Somalia, Yemen, Pakistan, India, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the Philippine states, while Uzbekistan ranked 134th out of 164 countries in this list compared to with Ukraine 36, Russia 39, Tajikistan 45, Kazakhstan 93, Azerbaijan 112. [1]

Uzbekistan is considered one of the countries facing the threats of terrorism and its harmful consequences.

Including: 1994-1997, 1999, 2000, 2004-2005, 2009 The subversive actions of recent years have brought grief to dozens, hundreds of families as a result of murders, raids and subversive actions aimed at the physical destruction of religious figures and law enforcement officers.

Despite the fact that no terrorist acts have been carried out in our country in recent years, superficial secular and religious knowledge, ignorance of the true content of purely religious concepts of Yohud, socio-material difficulties, religious extremist currents as a result of the decline of marriage relations of Jaraj and ideas such as "land" blasphemy", "exile", "jihad",

"martyrdom", "restoration of the caliphate" were imposed by terrorist organizations and groups "go away"., participation in hostilities in the ranks of militants of international terrorist organizations, The participation of persons of Uzbek origin in terrorist acts in the United States, Sweden, Turkey and other foreign countries, the re-criminalization of persons convicted of crimes related to terrorism and extremism after serving their sentences indicates that it is not enough to hold them accountable for eliminating this problem.

The development of more effective measures aimed at preventing and suppressing extremism and terrorism, combining efforts in this direction at the national and international levels, is one of the important directions of state policy.

In his address to the Supreme Assembly on December 29, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "In the context of conflicts that are observed in near and remote regions, complex processes taking place in the world, we must further accelerate our work to ensure peace and security in our country." [2]

It should be noted that various extremist and terrorist organizations continue their activities aimed at destabilizing the socio-political situation in the Central Asian republics. In this regard, the head of our State will draw the attention of the world community to further strengthen practical cooperation in order to ensure security and stability in Central Asia, effectively combat the threats of terrorism and extremism, transnational crime and drug trafficking within the framework of United Nations mechanisms, as well as the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, as far as possible to ensure within the framework of practical cooperation mechanisms between the countries of the region, It is aimed at the need to abandon the division of security threats into "own and others", practically adhere to the principle of "integrated security".

Today, one fact can be said with firm confidence: the new national system formed in Uzbekistan fully justifies itself in the current alarming situation, when a conflict of various risks and negativity is growing in the world.

We can consider my above words as another evidence that the speeches of the President of our country from international rostrums are warmly welcomed by the public, international experts, highly appreciated by other heads of State and Government, diplomats, a number of ideas and proposals are accepted and aimed at implementation.

In particular, a special resolution entitled "Education and religious tolerance" was adopted at the plenary session of the UN General Assembly. The draft document developed by Uzbekistan was unanimously supported by all UN member states. The adoption of the resolution was a practical expression of the initiative put forward by our President.

In December 2020, the U.S. Department of State removed Uzbekistan from its special religious freedom watch list. Assessing this process, former Secretary of the U.S. Department of State M. Pompeo noted that "Uzbekistan can become an example for other countries."

On October 13, 2020, Uzbekistan was elected to the UN Human Rights Council for the first time in history. In these elections, Uzbekistan was mentioned among the countries with the highest number of votes. It also shows that Uzbekistan's approaches to solving the pressing problems of extremism and the fight against terrorism, based on ensuring human rights and freedoms, are recognized by the international community.

Also in recent years, organizational measures have been taken in our country to combat the threats of terrorism and extremism, a number of national programs and regulatory legal acts have been adopted and put into practice.

In particular, in 2018, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On countering extremism" was adopted. It establishes the implementation of measures to prevent extremism as the main directions of state policy in this area, including increasing the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, forming an uncompromising attitude towards extremism in society, while eliminating the causes and conditions that allow it to arise.

Considering that 60% of the population of our republic is young people, a special policy has been developed for young citizens, and a number of works are being carried out within the framework of this policy. The Uzbek model of combating extremism and terrorism, which has attracted the attention of many foreign experts, pays special attention to the "struggle for thought" among young people through the promotion of foreign culture, religious and moral education. Systematic work is also being carried out on social rehabilitation and the return to normal life of citizens who have fallen under the influence of extremist ideas and realized their mistake. [2]

For the purpose of social rehabilitation of homeless citizens and their return to a healthy lifestyle, more than 20,000 citizens influenced by the ideas of fanaticism were excluded from the "Black List", and the practice of maintaining such lists was completely discontinued. [3]

Based on the humanitarian principle, 1,791 civilians were pardoned and released from penal institutions, regretting their actions among them, who committed crimes in the fight against terrorism and extremism, in order to express their disappointment to convicts who embarked on the path of strict correction. Of the 1800 Salkam people, 819 were completely released from the execution of sentences imposed by the court, and 439 were released on parole. In addition, 89 sentences were commuted to correctional labor, while 444 sentences were commuted.

Of those pardoned, 396 are women and 159 are men over the age of 60. Of these, 54 women were completely released from serving their sentences, and 90 were released early. In addition, while the unserved sentences of 41 women were commuted to correctional labor, the unserved sentences of 211 women were commuted. 54 of these men were fully released from serving their sentences, 78 were paroled, and 27 were reduced to unserved sentences. [4]

In the early period of our country's independence, when only an amnesty act was issued on the occasion of Independence Day or the Constitution, now a new approach has introduced the tradition of pardoning on other important dates (Ramadan, Nowruz and others).

In the following years, special attention is paid to the protection of human interests in our country, their rights and freedoms. After all, this is a sign that every citizen of Uzbekistan is under the protection of our state and has a firm expression in our head.

In this sense, the humanitarian opera "Mehr" is being conducted on behalf of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev and under his direct supervision in order to support our compatriots who have fallen into difficult conditions in foreign countries, return them to our country and ensure full adaptation in our society.

The main purpose of this is to create conditions for people of this category to feel protected and cared for by the state as full-fledged citizens. Therefore, the widespread use of the method of administrative and criminal prosecution of citizens with a relatively high level of danger to the state and society can have the opposite effect and cause them to become even more embittered and act against the state.

It holds a special place among the world community, in particular, among the countries of Central Asia.

In particular, on March 3-5, 2020, at a conference in Tashkent and Termez with the participation of officials from Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and

Tajikistan, effective and practical proposals were developed that could apply the "Uzbek experience" on religious rehabilitation and reintegration in Uzbekistan in other Central Asian countries.

As a conclusion, we can say that the change in attitudes in the field of combating extremism, on the one hand, is bearing fruit from the point of view of security, and on the other, as a result of reforms, citizens' trust in the government is increasing, as well as comprehensive reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan to combat crimes in the form of terrorism and extremism, prevent

Of course, such confessions encourage us to speed up the work even more, to try once again to achieve the desired efficiency.

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